

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF *INDRALUPTA* AND *KHALITYA* WITH *VIDDHA KARMA* (A PARA-SURGICAL PROCEDURE) AND INTERNAL MEDICATIONS: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

According to modern science hair fall is one of the main symptoms which indicate many pathological conditions. It may occur due to hormonal disturbance. In Ayurveda there is no clear description about the causative factors of *Indralupta*, *Khalitya* except *Acharya Charaka* and *Vagbhata* who has mentioned the major factors. *Viddha karma* therapy is an ancient ayurvedic para surgical procedure mentioned in *Sushruta Samhita*. It is a pain-less ayurvedic treatment for the *khalitya* and *indralupta*. In the classics of Ayurveda, the treatment of *khalitya* is divided in two parts – local and systemic. *Acharyas* mentioned *Siravedh* or *Prachhan* for the treatment of *khalitya*, *Indralupta*. In the *Samprapti* of *khalitya Roga*, vitiated *Rakta* and *Kapha* obstruct the hair follicle and leads to hair loss. *Pracchana karma*, *Suchivedhan karma* is indicated in *Raktaj Vyadhi* and helps to drain the Vitiated *Rakta* ultimately break the pathogenesis.

KEYWORDS: *Indralupta*, *Khalitya*, Hairfall, *Viddha karma*, Alopecia, *Kshudra roga*.

INTRODUCTION

In Ayurveda, *Indralupta* and *Khalitya* means hairfall. *Khalitya* and *Indralupta* is primarily a *Pitta* and *Kapha* dominant *Tridoshjanya Vyadhi* means these *vyadhis* have involvement of all the *doshas* viz., *Vata*, *Pitta*, *Kapha* alongwith *Rakta dosha* with the dominance of *Pitta* and *Kapha*. In Ayurveda Hair fall or loss of hair termed as *Khalitya*.^[1] *Acharya Sushruta* classified it under *Kshudraroga*^[2] and *Acharya Vagbhata* mentioned it under *Shiroroga*.^[3]

According to modern science it is termed as Alopecia or baldness. Alopecia areata, an autoimmune disease characterised by hair loss can be correlated with *Indralupta* in Ayurveda. Alopecia areata is an autoimmune disease characterized by hair loss on body especially on scalp without any clinical inflammatory signs. Due to side effects and limitation of the contemporary science, some harmless and effective medicines are expected from Alternative medical sciences. Ayurveda has great potential to treat such autoimmune diseases. Most of the people know alopecia to be a form of hair loss. However, there are three main types of the condition – Alopecia Areata, Alopecia Totalis and Alopecia Universalis. Alopecia is the medical term for baldness. Areata means patchy. This patchy baldness can develop anywhere on the body, including the scalp, beard area. Alopecia totalis: The person loses all hair on the scalp, so the scalp is completely bald. Alopecia universalis (AU) is a condition characterized by the complete loss of hair on the scalp and body. It is an advanced form of alopecia areata, a condition that causes round patches of hair loss.

Concept of beauty (*Saundarya*) is gaining more and more attention globally and hair plays an important role. It is a partial or complete loss of hair especially from the scalp. Hair adds to the beauty and the personality of a human being. Baldness is a curse for one's look and personality.

Prevalence of hair fall was found to be 60.3%, prevalence of dandruff was found to be 17.1% and the prevalence of baldness was found to be 50.4%. It is a universal problem affecting both sexes of all races. *Khalitya* is commonly seen in the age group of 18-40 years. According to survey, up to 40% of men and 25% of women in India are victims of hair fall. It is a slowly progressing disorder.

Khalitya and *Indralupta* are mainly *Pitta* dominant *Tridoshaja Vyadhi*.^[4] Where *Tejas Mahabhoota* combining with *Vatadi Dosha* reaches the *Shira Kapala* and cause hair fall by *Dahana* of *Roma Koopa* (hair follicles).^[5] *Indralupta* and *Ruhyam* these are 2 words which are also described in *Ayurveda* as a symptom of Hair fall.^[6] According to *Acharya Charaka*, the *Tejas Dhatu* (heat) of the body in association with *Vayu* and other *Dosha*, scorches up the hair-root (scalp) giving instantaneous rise to *Indralupta* (alopecia). According to *Acharya Kartika*, falling of hair from all over the body is called *Ruhyam*.

There are some differences between *Khalitya* & *Indralupta*. In *Khalitya*, hair loss is gradual and generalised over the scalp but hair is lost suddenly and patch by patch in *Indralupta*.^[7]

In present era, millions of people are suffering from hair fall. It is progressing disorder among people living in sedentary life, changing lifestyle, unhealthy dietary habits, sleep disturbances, systemic diseases, medications, stressful life and deficiencies in the body which directly reflect in loss of hair.

According to modern science hair fall is one of the main symptoms which indicate many pathological conditions. It may occur due to hormonal disturbance. In Ayurveda there is no clear description about the causative factors of *Indralupta*, *Khalitya* except *Acharya Charaka* and *Vagbhata* who has mentioned the major factors as follows- *Pitta Prakruti*, *Kshara-atisevan*, *Lavan rasa atisevan*, *Ushar Bhoomi*, *Viruddha Ahara sevan*^[8], ignorance of *Pratishyaya*^[9], *Lavan atisevan* during pregnancy would be result in congenital hair loss (*Khalitya*). *Acharya Vagbhata* has mentioned *Shiroroga* under the caption of *Urdhvajatrugata Vyadhi* and these are further divided into *Kapalagata Vyadhi*, *Khalitya* being one of them.^[10]

There is pain less ayurvedic treatment for the *khalitya* and *indralupta* i.e *Viddha karma* which is described in *Sushruta Samhita*. *Viddha karma* therapy is an ancient ayurvedic para surgical procedure mentioned in *Sushruta Samhita*. *Viddhakarma* is a quick result promising treatment modality and a blessing to whole living kingdom. Ayurveda blessed us with multiple effective and harmless treatments and medications. *Viddha karma* is one of the 8 *Shastrakarma*.^[11] In *Viddha karma* the points are pierced with special a hollow needle which leads to painful mechanical stimulus which causes release of endorphins thereby, causing immediate pain relief. *Viddha Karma* is a para surgical procedure which removes the locally accumulated Doshas in the human body via a pricking procedure. Piercing the point with special hallow needle (no 26 and 1/2-inch, 0.45 breath and 13mm length).

Viddha karma, also known as *vedhan chikitsa*, is the treatment of puncturing or piercing certain points that reduces pain and also helps to reverse the mechanism of pathology in certain possible way. It is also known as *suchivedhan*.

Now a days, *viddhakarma* has come to major treatment stream and has become widely popular day by day in pain management and is used as main therapy in the management of musculoskeletal disorder like backache, shoulder joint pain, cervical pain, lumber pain etc. also skin disorder like eczematous patches, dandruff etc.

In the ancient text described, *Pitta* along with *Vata* by involving the *Romakupas* (roots of hair) causes hairfall and there after *Kapha* along with *Rakta* obstructs the channel of *Romakupas* (roots of hair) leading to the blockage and stoppage of the regeneration of hair and this condition is known as *Khalitya*, *Indralupta*, or *Ruhyā*.^[12]

In Ayurveda classics, it is mentioned that *Vata-Pitta Dosha* reached at the root of hair and leads to *Khalitya*.^[13] The treatment of *khalitya* can be divided in two parts – local and systemic. *Acharyas* mentioned *Siravedh* or *Prachhan* for the treatment of *khalitya*, *Indralupta*. In the *Samprapti* of *khalitya* Roga, vitiated *Rakta* and *Kapha* obstruct the hair follicles and results hair loss. *Pracchana karma*, *Suchivedhan karma* is indicated in *Raktaj Vyadhi*.^[14] and helps to drain the Vitiated *Rakta*, ultimately break the pathogenesis.^[15]

CASE PRESENTATION

Patient Information

A 33-year-old male patient, working as a salesman at Amravati, Maharashtra, India. He is well built, with a height of 165 cm and weighing 62 kg.

Present Medical History

A 33-year-old male experienced itching of the scalp 13 years back. After a few months, he suffered from hair fall. Gradually he developed excessive hair loss of the scalp, like baldness. Thinning hair, hair loss, and mild scalp itching. Later, after a few days, he started noticing the patch of baldness at the parietal region of the head. He had undergone allopathic treatment, but that provided him only temporary relief. With these complaints, the patient approached the ayurvedic treatment on an OPD basis. The patient was advised to undergo viddha karma treatments every 7 days, specifically targeting the areas of the scalp with the most significant baldness.

Past Medical History

There was no relevant past history.

Family History

No member of the family had history of such illness.

Patient's personal history

Table no. 1: Personal history Ashtavidha Pariksha.

Diet	Both Vegetarian and non-vegetarian
Appetite	Good
Micturition	5-6 times/day and 0-1 time/night
Sleep	Sound sleep
Bowel habit	Irregular
Addiction	Tobacco chewing and alcohol consumption occasionally

Table no. 2: Ashtavidha pariksha.

Systemic Examination

<i>Nadi</i>	82 bpm
<i>Mutra</i>	<i>Samyaka</i>
<i>Mala</i>	<i>Sama</i>
<i>Jivha</i>	<i>Nirama</i>
<i>Shabda</i>	<i>Spasta</i>
<i>Sparsha</i>	<i>Samshitoshna</i>
<i>Drik</i>	<i>Spasta</i>

Table no. 3: Systemic examination.

Blood Pressure	120/80
Temperature	Afebrile
Pulse	74/bpm
Respiratory Rate	18/min
Weight	62kg
Height	5'6''
Sleep	sound
Gait	Normal

Ayurvedic interpretation of the Patient's condition

Diagnosis

In this particular case, the diagnosis was initially made, based on his symptoms. The final diagnosis was arrived at based on the vast literature available on *Khalitya*, *Indralupta* in the public domain and symptoms as reported by the patient. Hence, the case was diagnosed *Khalitya* (Hair fall) on the basis of sign and symptoms.

Treatment Protocol

1. *Shamana Chikitsa*
2. *Viddha karma*

1. *Shamana Chikitsa*

Drug Dose Frequency

1. *Gandhak Rasayan* 2BID before food with Luke warm water
2. *Bhrigarajasav* 15ml BID after food with Normal water
3. *Nilibhrungadi tail* 5ml For Local (scalp) application
4. *Amlaki Rasayana* 2gm OD at morning with Luke warm water

2. *Viddha karma*

Materials needed

1. Sterile needle no.26
2. Disposable gloves
3. Sterile gauze
4. Cotton.

Purva Karma

Local area was cleaned with warm water and wipe with sterile gauze piece. Procedure was explained to the patient in his own language and consent was taken.

Pradhana Karma

Viddha Karma is a para surgical procedure which removes the accumulated *Doshas* in the human body via a pricking procedure. Piercing the point with special hallows needle no 26 and 1/2-inch, 0.45 breath and 13mm length. Remove needle gently.

Pashchat Karma

The selected area was cleaned and the patient was advised not to take head bath for whole day and not to use any oil immediately after the hair wash or on the day of procedure. He was advised to avoid spicy and oily food, junk food, fast food and cold water and day sleeping. Also advised to stop tobacco chewing and alcohol consumption.

ASSESSMENT

Assessment was done after the completion of procedure and after the follow up. Both subjective as well as clinical improvements were employed for the assessment of the impact of the procedure. All symptoms which were selected for assessment, their improvements were thoroughly examined and the severity of each of them was rated before and after the trial of the procedure.

Subjective criteria**1. Keshpatan (Hair fall)**

1. No hair fall	0
2. Hair fall once in the morning while washing/ combing	1
3. Hair fall on every time of morning	2
4. Hair fall even without combing and raised hairline in frontal region (mild baldness)	3

2. Keshbhoomi Rukshata (Dryness)

1. Smooth hair surface	0
2. Occasional rough hair surface	1
3. Slight rough hair surface	2
4. Rough hair surface	3

3. Keshbhoomi Kandū (Itching)

1. Absent	0
2. Mild itching	1
3. Moderate itching	2
4. Severe itching	3

4. Darunaka (Dandruff)

1. Absent	0
2. Mild	1
3. Moderate	2
4. Severe	3

5. Keshvardhan (Hair Growth)

1. No Hair Growth	0
2. Mild Hair Growth	1
3. Moderate Hair Growth	2
4. Severe Hair Growth	3

OVERALL ASSESSMENT**Table no. 4: Assessment chart.**

Sr.no.	Symptoms	Before Viddha karma	After Viddha karma	After follow up
1	<i>Keshpatan</i> (Hair fall)	3	0	0
2	<i>Keshbhoomi Rukshata</i> (Dryness)	3	2	1
3	<i>Keshbhoomi Kandū</i> (Itching)	3	1	0
4	<i>Darunaka</i> (Dandruff)	2	1	1
5	<i>Keshvardhan</i> (Hair Growth)	0	1	2

Images

Before viddha karma treatment

Fig. 1

After viddha karma treatment
(After 7 days of treatment)

Fig. 2

After viddha karma treatment
(After 14 days of treatment)

Fig. 3

After viddha karma treatment
(After 21 days of treatment)

Fig. 4

DISCUSSION

Indralupta is a disease characterized by patches of hair loss spread throughout the body and scalp. It can be considered as alopecia areata according to conventional medical care. The present case report is on the effectiveness of *shodhana* (treatment in which aggravated doshas are expelled from the body) and *shaman* (treatment that pacifies the aggravated *doshas*) in the patient of *Indralupta*. *Khalitya* (Hairfall) is the most common condition in young and old age. In pathophysiology of *Khalitya*, there is involvement of *Rasa*, *Rakta Mamsa* and *Asthivaha Srotas*. Hair fall is a cosmetic disorder affecting patient psychologically. Millions of people worldwide suffering from hair loss. Most of the Research studies conducted on *Khalitya* are found on *Nasya*, *Raktamokshan*, *Basti*, local application and use of *Rasayan* drugs.

Alopecia areata is an autoimmune condition described clinically as transient, non-scarring hair loss on the body, especially on the scalp preserving the hair follicle. Clinical presentation

of hair loss can vary from loss in well-defined patches to diffuse or total hair loss termed as alopecia totalis or alopecia universalis, which can affect all hair-bearing sites.^[16]

In the *Charaka Samhita, Vimanasthana*, while describing the disorders occurring due to over indulgence in *Kshara, Lavana* and *Viruddha Ahara* has mentioned the occurrence of Hair Loss as a consequence. It has been mentioned that the *Viruddha Ahara* like, simultaneous intake of *Lavana* (salt) with milk in the diet induces *Indralupta*, as observed in the people of *Saurashtra* and *Bahluka*. Thus, it can be said that a person habituated to excessive *Lavana* or *Kshara* intake and taking *Viruddha Ahara* in routine is prone to have *Indralupta*.^[17] *Mithya Ahara* and *Vihara Manoabhighata* like mental stress, fright, anger, shock etc. may collectively increase the *Pitta* and *Vata Dosha*. The *Ushna* and *Tikshna* properties of *Pitta* get augmented whereas the *Vata* suffers an aggravation in *Ruksha, Khara* and *Chala* properties. Here an aggravated *Pitta (Bhrajaka Pitta)* supported by the vitiated *Dehoshma* burns the *Keshabhoomi* whereas an increased *Vata* gives rise to more frequent and comparatively prolonged *Shira Sankocha* by its *Ruksha* and *Khara Guna*. The *Snigdhatva* and the *Pichchhilatva* of the normal *Kapha Dosha* is prevalent throughout the pores of the skin so as to keep it soft and moist. By the augmentation of the *Ushna, Tikshna, Ruksha* and *Khara* properties of *Pitta* and *Vata Doshas* respectively, the *Sneha* and the *Pichchhilatva* of the *Kapha Dosha* are dried up within the pores of the skin of the scalp thus, obstructing the growth of new hairs, causing *Indralupta*.

There is management of pain less ayurvedic treatment for the *Khalitya* and *Indralupta* is *Viddha karma* i.e described in *Sushruta Samhita*. *Viddha karma* therapy is an ancient ayurvedic para surgical procedure mentioned in *Sushruta Samhita*. *Viddha karma* is a parasurgical procedure which removes the accumulated doshas in the human body via a pricking procedure.

In the pathophysiology of *Indralupta and khalitya* vitiated *Pitta* along with *Vata* gets lodged at the site of *Romakoopa* (hair follicles) resulting in the destruction of hairs. Later, *Rakta* and *Kapha* causes obstruction resulting in hindering of hair growth.^[18-19] As per Ayurveda concepts, impaired melanin production and impairment in hair production can be compared to *Dhatwagnimandya* (impaired metabolism) at *Majja* and *Asthidhatu* (bone) level since *Agni* (digestive fire) is responsible for the *Dhatu* transformation, formation of *Kitta* and *Upadhatu*.^[20]

Pathophysiology of *Indralupta and khalitya* break by *viddha karma* in which removes the accumulated *Doshas* in the scalp. Piercing the point with special hallows needle no 26 and 1/2-inch, 0.45 breath and 13mm length. Remove needle gently. Here multiple pricks are made on the skin using needle to produce mild capillary bleeding which can stimulate the hair follicles resulting in hair growth and also *shaman chikitsa* works more effective in this case. *Mode of action of Shaman chikitsa* is *Nilibhrungadi Tail* used as a local application overhead which has *Keshya* and *Rasayana* properties. This oil also enhances the nutritive beneficial effect on the hair. The *Nilibhrungadi Tail* is likely to stimulate the anagen phase (growth phage) and re-growth of hairs and this purpose is achieved by local application of oil over head due to deeper absorption. The combination of *Amalaki Rasayan*, *Bhrungarajasav* and *gandhak rasayan* work as a *Rasayana* which help in *Keshavridhhi* and rejuvenation. These drugs are possessing *Tridoshhara* property, *Agnideepana*, *Krimihara* action. There by promoting hair growth along with overall wellness of the body.

CONCLUSION

The present case of *Indralupta and khalitya* is successfully treated with Ayurvedic medications and *viddha karma*. This case report shows the possibility of natural re-pigmentation of grey hair through Ayurveda treatment.

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Conflict of Interest

None.

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